

Part 1 Key Characteristics of the Participants

Explanation: Please mark ✓ into about yourself

1. Name
2. Address.....

(Items 1 and 2 are for sending prizes by mail, in case of being randomly selected as a lucky winner.

If you do not wish to win a prize, you are still eligible to participate without needing to fill in this section.)

3. Sex
 Male Female Not specified
4. Age range (15-59 years)
 18-25 year 26-33 year 34-41 year 42-49 year 50 years or more.

5. Types of people with disabilities
 Visually impaired These include blindness or blurred vision.
 Mobility or physical disability

6. Recent experience in receiving public services

'Public Service' refers to services provided by the public sector for people with disabilities, covering all aspects such as education, employment, living conditions (housing, sidewalks, sports fields, public transportation, green and safe public spaces), registration of people with disabilities, and welfare services from the government (subsistence allowance, sign language interpretation services, provision of necessary tools or equipment, medical or vocational rehabilitation), as well as access to information and communication technology.

- 1-3 months ago More than 3 months More than 1 year

7. Public Services You Have Used (You can choose more than one)

- Registration of people with disabilities Education Working
 Election Access to government websites or applications
 Residential services (e.g., housing, sidewalks, sports fields, public transportation, public spaces, green and safe spaces)
 Receiving welfare from the government (e.g., subsistence allowance, sign language interpretation services, necessary tools or equipment, medical or vocational rehabilitation)

8. Residential Province Area

- Chiang Mai Phitsanulok Khon Kaen Nakhon Ratchasima
 Nonthaburi chon buri Surat Thani Songkhla

Part 2 The relationship of public services for people with disabilities to audit data governance

Explanation Consider the relationship of public services for people with disabilities to governance. Identify which level of verification data matches the description provided and mark ✓ in only one field that corresponds to your level of agreement, divided into the following levels:

5 means strongly agree.

4 means agree.

3 means unsure.

2 means disagree.

1 means strongly disagree.

Article	Topic	Level					For Researchers
		5	4	3	2	1	
1	The government has set a joint plan and clearly assigned the person responsible for providing public services for people with disabilities.						s001
2	The agencies responsible for providing public services for people with disabilities are adequately allocated budgets. The results are followed up and checked.						s002
3	The government has a policy to provide information and information technology services for people with disabilities. By clearly assigning the agency responsible for providing services, such as the service of issuing identification cards for people with disabilities on the website of the Department of Promotion and Development of the quality of life of people with disabilities.						s003
4	The agencies responsible for providing information and information technology services for people with disabilities have been allocated adequate budgets. For example, service centers for people with disabilities nationwide have been allocated sufficient budgets for disability identification services. The results were followed up by the Department of Promotion and Development of the Quality of Life of						s004

Article	Topic	Level					For Researchers
		5	4	3	2	1	
	people with disabilities and audited by the Office of the Auditor General.						
5	He was satisfied with the overall quality of public services for people with disabilities.						s005
6	There is a central agency in your province that coordinates cooperation between government agencies and public services for people with disabilities.						s006
7	The process of public services for people with disabilities has taken less time and become easier.						s007
8	There is a law to support the procedure for providing public services for people with disabilities.						s008
9	It uses available resources economically and cost-effectively.						s009
10	There is a law on comprehensive and adequate public services for people with disabilities.						s010
11	The quality of public services is regularly monitored against centrally used resources.						s011
12	There is a report on the cost-effectiveness of public services for people with disabilities compared to the resources used.						s012
13	Public services for people with disabilities in Thailand comply with international standards, such as the United Nations Universal Design Standard, in the design of products, environments, and services so that everyone can use them equally without modification or specialized design.						s013
14	You can use electronic or digital signatures in the process of public services for people with disabilities.						s014
15	Government agencies, public service providers have the tools to manage quality services.						s015

Article	Topic	Level					For Researchers
		5	4	3	2	1	
16	There are consultation services recommended by government agencies, public services for people with disabilities.						s016
17	Disability registration information is stored in a completely digital format (100%) without paper recording.						s017
18	Government agencies exchange information on people with disabilities in accordance with the framework of collaboration in public services.						s018
19	There is a one-stop service for people with disabilities in your area.						s019
20	The disability statistics dataset is publicly available at no additional cost.						s020
21	There are websites of government agencies and public service providers to communicate information with people with disabilities.						s021
22	Public service government websites are tested against the accessible websites standards (WCAG).						s022
23	You are satisfied with the access to general public services for people with disabilities.						s023
24	You are satisfied with access to public services for people with disabilities through digital channels, such as access to government information through the website or access to services through applications.						s024
25	You are satisfied with the time and cost of accessing public services for people with disabilities.						s025

Part 3 Audit Data Governance

Explanation Consider how well the audit data governance matches the text described, and then mark it. ✓ into only one field that matches your comment level, divided into: 5
The levels are as follows:

5 means strongly agree.

4 means agree.

3 means unsure.

2 means disagree.

1 means strongly disagree.

Information Governance It means defining the rights, duties and responsibilities of stakeholders in the management of government information at all stages to ensure the correct acquisition and use of information of government agencies. The information is complete and up-to-date. Maintain privacy, be able to link, exchange, and integrate information between each other effectively and securely and securely. To support the use of data primarily in government administration and public services.

Master data means that the data that is created is the basic information that is important for operations to be shared within the organization and drive the organization to achieve its goals, such as employee data, organizational structure data, etc.

Reference data means information that is created or referenced from the main data to be standardized and widely shared. The source that can be used for reference is clearly indicated, such as provincial name information, postal code information, country code information, etc.

Article	Topic	Level					For Researchers
		5	4	3	2	1	
1	If audits have good data governance, they can protect individuals or communities.						a001
2	If the audit has good data governance, it can build confidence in the information system.						a002
3	If the audit has good data governance, data security can be ensured.						a003

Article	Topic	Level					For Researchers
		5	4	3	2	1	
4	If the audit has good data governance, it will enhance the information system and services.						a004
5	Audit data governance affects master and reference data.						a005
6	Audit data governance affects the design and development of data models to better explain the characteristics of data architecture and function.						a006
7	If audits have good data governance, it promotes information sharing and collaboration.						a007
8	Audit data governance affects big data management.						a008
9	Audit data governance affects in-depth analysis to meet research needs (Data Science).						a009
10	Audit data governance affects the adoption of data with new digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI).						a010
11	If audits have good data governance, it facilitates innovation.						a011
12	Audit data governance affects data set description management.						a012
13	If the audit has good data governance, it can determine the rights and ownership of the data.						a013
14	If audits have good data governance, it promotes equal benefits from the data.						a014
15	Audit data governance affects data quality.						a015

Part 4 Data-driven culture

Explanation Consider the level at which the data-driven culture described in the following statements matches your understanding, and then mark the appropriate field. Please select only one option that best reflects your view.

5 means strongly agree.

4 means agree.

3 means unsure.

2 means disagree.

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Article	Topic	Level					For Researchers
		5	4	3	2	1	
1	Data leadership, which inspires and advocates for data use, from collection to data-driven decision-making, influences the governance of audit data.						c001
2	If there is a clear career path and incentives for data analysts to excel and feel satisfied, it will foster data leaders within the organization.						c002
3	An organizational culture that does not support leaders or personnel who do not use data to make decisions, such as an Anti-HiPPO culture, affects audit data governance.						c003
4	Executives who frequently make decisions based on instinct or experience, without considering the available data, hinder the effectiveness of audit data governance.						c004
5	An organizational culture that emphasizes error analysis through repetition and flexibility (Iterative, Learning Culture) affects the governance of audit data.						c005

Article	Topic	Level					For Researchers
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6	An organization with a culture of questioning and inquiry, especially when things are not fully understood (Inquisitive, Questioning Culture), influences audit data governance.						c006
7	An organizational culture where leaders set clear metrics for their team to achieve common goals (Goals-First Culture) influences the governance of audit data.						c007
8	An open, trusting culture positively influences audit data governance.						c008
9	An organization that supports data analysis training for personnel at all levels and promotes intelligent communication within teams creates a broad, reliable corporate culture.						c009
10	When government officials adhere to ethics in data management—starting from creation to storage—Data Handling Ethics will impact the governance of audit data.						c010

Part 1 Key Characteristics of the Participants

Explanation: Please mark ✓ into about yourself

1. Sex

Male Female Not specified

2. Age range (15-59 years)

18-25 year 26-33 year 34-41 year 42-49 year 50 years or more.

3. Types of Government Officials

Government officials from policy-level organizations (provincial service centers for people with disabilities)

Government officials from organizations at the policy implementation level (local government organizations)

Government officials from audit-level organizations (Office of the Auditor General)

4. Experience in Providing Public Services for People with Disabilities

"Public Service" refers to the provision of services by the public sector that cover all aspects for people with disabilities, including education, employment, housing (e.g., housing, sidewalks, sports fields, public transportation, green spaces, and safe public spaces). It also includes the registration of people with disabilities, welfare services (e.g., subsistence allowance for people with disabilities, sign language interpretation services, provision of necessary tools or equipment, and medical or vocational rehabilitation), as well as access to elections and information and communication technology.

1-5 Years 6-10 Years 10 years and above

5. Residential Province Area

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